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“LIFE AND LESSONS FROM CAST AWAY”

Have you ever found yourself dreaming that you're stuck somewhere completely strange and unfamiliar? A place that's deafeningly quiet as if no one has been there but only you. You quickly pick up the fact that you're a survivor of an accident and are stranded on an island. Luckily for us, it's only in a dream. Unfortunately, for Chuck Noland, the main character of the movie *Cast Away*, this entire scenario occurred in his life in the movie. So, who is Chuck and what is *Cast Away* all about?

Cast Away is a movie released in the year 2000. It was about a devoted FedEx manager named Chuck Noland who got stranded on an island after the delivery plane that he boarded crashed into the Pacific. Chuck was very frustrated with his situation at first but sometime later, he realized he should not let his emotions get to him. So, with his loneliness on the island alongside FedEx packages that somehow helped him stay alive, he persevered, fought for his life, and applied resourcefulness and strategic thinking, hoping that he could live long enough until someday he'd get out of that situation.

Many months passed. Even if his new life felt as if he were starting over again, he was able to live and adapt to hardcore survival. However, to adapt to this new life didn't mean all was solved. He still had to make a lot of trials and errors to escape and bring himself back to civilization. After several attempts, he found the final opportunity to escape and fortunately, that was the last and successful attempt for him as he was found. Finally, after spending almost 1,500 nights alone on an island, he found his way home but discovered that the girlfriend he left before his flight 4 years ago was now married with children, as she thought that Chuck had died in the crash.

As hurtful as his story ended, we can still find something to learn and be encouraged by. Everything that Chuck went through can be reflected on how we humans should handle our lives or even on how businessmen handle their business. Similar to how Chuck's story was not in his control, in reality, life and business are also not in our hands and everything happens unexpectedly unless ill-manneredly manipulated. We can only control some parts but most is according to how destiny is written for us. In life alone, I can remember when my mama tita, whom I treated like my own mom, passed away when I was in college. I could remember how she was so well but then unexpectedly, like how Chuck's plane went down and crashed, so was my mommy's life. I was too young to know enough about life and how much I should appreciate it.

Looking back, if only I knew she'd be gone, I would've shown her much more love than I normally did. After she passed, I was in grief. She took care of me for so long that we were closer compared to her biological children. I didn't know what to do but, just like how Chuck dealt with his devastating situation, I learned and

adapted many lessons to live by. Because of that, the memory of her and her death is there but the pain is lessened. In addition, in terms of business, the most important point we should take from the story is how Chuck managed all the unexpected situations. In business, success cannot be clearly determined and threats may come. Similar to how he never thought he'd be stranded after boarding the plane, businessmen also won't know when the storm will hit their business and threaten them with bankruptcy. Therefore, at all times, businessmen should always have backup plans to prepare for any sort of uncertainty and also, in case they are already put near the edge of failure, they should learn from Chuck who could've easily given up but rather, he became resourceful, strong, and used all his capabilities to survive and make a successful escape.

Businesses should not be easy to give up but rather look for other opportunities to improve or strategies to save their company. Lastly, like how Chuck returned home but in a different setting where his supposed-to-be girlfriend was now married to another man, businessmen should also expect that sometimes, results of hard work won't always go as planned and destiny may lead you down a different path. Thus, you should not be discouraged but only take this as an open door to start thinking about another goal.

